

substantial supply of residual moisture and the low initial weed population. Rice was cut close to the ground and gramoxone herbicide was applied. Seed of soybeans and mung beans were dibbled. Plots were weeded twice by hand. Insects were adequately controlled by two sprayings of carbofuran, followed by three sprayings of methomyl whenever initial pest damage was observed.

Varieties that yielded significantly higher than others were soybean Kuro daizu; mung beans CES 1 D-21, E.G. Glabrous #3, CES 55, and Dau Mo; and cowpeas E.G. #3, E.G. #2, and TVu4-b-b-10-b (see table). Yields were almost as high as those of the same crops grown with good tillage under upland conditions. Yields of the high yielding legumes ranged from 4 to 88% higher

than those of the checks. All crops matured within 71 to 81 days; mung beans generally matured earliest, followed by cowpeas, then soybeans. Soybean plants were shorter and matured earlier than usual because of photoperiod reaction. The cowpea crop, which was not mulched, did not grow as tall as mung beans. The mung bean crop, which was mulched, had a better supply of moisture.

A novel strategy of intercropping in traditional lowland rice fields to maximize food production

K. I. James, rice breeder; R. R. Nair, junior agronomist, Rice Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala, India

Intercropping is well suited for small farmers who seek to maximize production by having one or more crops on every square meter of land all year round. Little work has been done on intercropping in lowland rice fields where the traditional practice is to raise two or more crops of rice in tandem sequence. The feasibility of raising high-value crops in the traditional wetlands was studied during the rabi season (Feb.–May) of 1976–77 at the Rice Research Station, Pattambi.

A rice field of 574.8 sq m was divided into two parts. In one (245.5 sq m), the rice variety Triveni was transplanted. In the other part (329.3 sq m) the intercropping study was conducted. Ash gourd, cucumber, okra, and cowpea were planted on raised beds 16.5 m long, 1.5 m wide, and 10 cm high. The distance between two beds was 2 m. Four such beds occupied 99 sq m. On all sides of the beds, Triveni was transplanted as in the other portion of the field. The net area of rice in the intercropped field was 230.3 sq m.

Cucumber and ash gourd were raised in polythene cups and 18- to 20-day-old seedlings were transplanted in the raised beds immediately after planting rice to reduce the cropping time in the main field. Okra was seeded directly between each two cucumber and ash gourd seedlings. Cowpea was sown on the borders of all beds. Vegetables were not irrigated, as sufficient moisture was

available in their root zones by capillary rise from the rice fields where the soil was kept under shallow submergence (2–5 cm).

The rice crop yielded 107.8 kg grain (4.4 t/ha) and 169.0 kg straw (6.9 t/ha), while the rice crop surrounding the vegetables produced 96.1 kg grain (4.2 t/ha) and 139.1 kg straw (6.1 t/ha). Vegetable production from the

intercropped area was 307.1 kg (31.0 t/ha). Thus, the total food production with intercropping was 12.24 tons vs. 4.39 tons from the sole crop of rice, an increase in overall productivity of 170.8%. The study indicates a tremendous potential for increasing food production from wetland rice fields. The investigation is being continued on a large scale at Pattambi.

Machinery development & testing.

Manually operated diaphragm pump developed at BRRI

Mohammad Abdul Baqui, scientific officer, and Fred E. Nichols, agricultural engineer, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

The agricultural engineering division of the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute

(BRRI) has developed a manually operated diaphragm pump for low-cost irrigation. The pump has an average discharge capacity of 8,925 liters/hour and an optimum lifting head of 4.65 m (see table). It is made of steel sheets.

The cost of making one unit is roughly Tk 545 (US\$37) — low enough that poor

Upward movement of the handle causes the pump's diaphragm to expand and thus draw water from a well or a stream through a common manifold and into the pump chamber. Compression of the diaphragm forces the water from the chamber. Directional movement of water is controlled by a set of simple flapper valves on the inlet and outlet side.

Test results of diaphragm pump using 2-inch discharge and suction pipes with 25.4 x 25.4-inch boxes (no. of strokes taken at normal operating conditions). Bangladesh Rice Research Institute.

Observation (no.)	Vertical lift (m)	Frictional loss (m)	Total head (m)	Length of stroke (cm)	Discharge (liter/stroke)	Strokes (no./min)	Discharge (liter/min)	Discharge (liter/h)
1	1.86	1.05	2.9	5.8	5.4	65	348	20,893
2	2.79	0.93	3.1	5.8	5.4	62	303	19,732
3	3.70	0.68	4.4	5.8	5.4	50	265	15,897

farmers can buy one to irrigate their fragmented holdings. The pump can be handled by only two men. Its most significant feature is ease of operating. Even unskilled persons can operate it and repair it with locally available inner tubes.

The pump may help to extend the area of modern rice cultivation in Bangladesh, which is seriously handicapped because of nonavailability or high cost of irrigation water during the boro (winter) season. *W*

that are easy to incorporate into F₁ hybrids.

The success of using hybrids for rice production depends on the ability to multiply the male-sterile lines and to mass-produce hybrid seed. Valuable developments in China include the use of more female plants (rows), tearing of the leaf sheath that encloses the panicle, cutting the flag leaves, applying growth regulators, and supplementary pollination. In Hunan, 3,300 ha of hybrid seed produced an average of 530 kg hybrid seed/ha. In Han-yan county, 465 ha produced 750 kg seed/ha. Because hybrid rice has high tillering ability, only 1 or 2 seedlings/hill are planted. Only 7.5 to 15 kg seed/ha are needed for planting, so 1 ha of a hybrid seed farm supplies enough seed to plant from 30 to 50 ha of farm fields. Hybrid rice is now growing or is being tested on large areas in Kiangsi, Kwangtung, Kwangsi, Fukien, Hsinking, and Liaoning provinces, as well as in Hunan. Yields have increased significantly in these regions.

Problems that remain to be resolved or improved upon include:

1. The male-sterile cytoplasm of both indica and keng (japonica) rices comes from wild rice or from ordinary cultivars. The use of hybrid rice is still limited because of the difficulties of obtaining the restorers and the insufficient combinations with strong hybrid vigor. By crossing the variety Ping-ai 58 (female) with a wild rice from South China and then making other crosses, a sterile line of "type 0" (like type 0 blood) was recently developed in Kiangsi. Its sterility is stable and many restorers have been found. In fact, many keng or indica rices can be used as restorers and they have strong hybrid vigor.

2. The most common hybrid rices, Nan-u 1, Nan-u 2, and Nan-u 3, have low disease resistance, which should be improved.

3. The long growth duration of the hybrid rices now used make them unsuitable for the cropping patterns in many areas.

Chemically and naturally male-sterile lines have been used to develop hybrid

Too late for

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Rice breeding in China

Notes from a seminar given by Mr. Lin Shih-Cheng, plant breeder and member of the Rice Research Team of the Agricultural Association of The Peoples Republic of China, visiting IRRI, 17 October 1977

Rice breeding in the People's Republic of China recently reached a new plateau with the exploitation of hybrid vigor, or heterosis, to increase yields. Because rice is a self-pollinated crop, to exploit the hybrid vigor of the F₁ for rice production, one must find three lines for seed production – the cytoplasmic male-sterile line or A-line, the maintainer or Bline, and the fertility-restorer or R-line.

The program in China to utilize hybrid vigor began in 1964 when instructors and students at the Chan-yang Agricultural School, Hunan province, found a male sterile rice plant in a field and began to study it. To obtain three lines, they crossed the male-sterile plant with thousands of cultivars but were unable to find a maintainer.

In 1970, an instructor at the Chan-yang School discovered a wild male-sterile rice plant on Hainan island. By continuously backcrossing it with cultivated varieties, and selecting progeny lines, stable male-sterile lines and

maintainer lines were developed by 1972.

In 1973, after testing many crosses, the Kiangsi Agricultural College found a restorer with strong hybrid vigor. At the same time, several other restorers with strong hybrid vigor were isolated; Restorer 1 (Thai 1) was isolated in Kiangsi province; Restorer 2 (IR24), in Kwangtung; and Restorer 3 (IR661), in Hunan. The major hybrids have been tested in different areas with good results. In 1976, hybrid rice was planted on 133,000 ha in China – 87,000 ha were in Hunan. The hybrids generally yielded from 20 to 30% higher than conventional varieties. In some fields, yields reached about 10 t/ha. Yields of 11.3 to 12 t/ha have been reported.

Hybrid rices have strong root systems, high absorption capacity, high tillering ability, high vegetative vigor, and large panicles. During later growth, the dry matter accumulation is far higher than respiration losses. For that reason, hybrid rice yields higher than conventional varieties under the same environmental conditions.

Hybrid rice offers better chances for incorporating multiple disease and insect resistance and for increasing the spectrum of resistance to certain diseases such as blast because the resistance to most major pests is controlled by dominant genes